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Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia

DEVELOPING A STUDENT NURSE ANESTHETIST MENTORSHIP PROGRAM

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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By

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ABSTRACT

Student registered nurse anesthetists (SRNAs) experience significant anxiety and stress during their three years of doctoral education. As a result, SRNAs may display burnout and fatigue, resulting in program attrition, poor mental health and well-being, and suicidal ideation (Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). A review of the literature suggests that medical students and other allied health professionals receiving mentorship have decreased stress, increased resilience, and may experience less distressing periods of transition between didactic and clinical demands (Akinla et al., 2018; Etzel et al., 2018; Nakhostin-Ansari et al., 2021). Although the benefits of mentorship have been studied in the medical school student and physician resident population, a gap exists in research that establishes the benefits of implementing evidence-based mentorship programs for SRNAs. This paper investigates evidence on peer mentorship in health professions and makes evidence-based recommendations for the creation of a tailored mentorship program to meet the needs of Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia (KPSA) students. This program does not currently have a formalized student mentorship program. Baseline mentorship satisfaction and perceived stress of current KPSA students were collected via an electronic survey using established research tools. Additionally, a needs assessment was conducted to establish themes among students' mentorship wants and needs. Recommendations for an evidence-based mentorship program have been devised for future implementation at KPSA to meet the needs of students, as revealed by their responses. Significant barriers to successful mentorship program implementation and future evaluation metrics of the mentorship program post-implementation are also discussed.

Keywords: Student registered nurse anesthetist (SRNA), well-being, mentorship, resilience.

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Background

Student registered nurse anesthetists (SRNAs) experience anxiety, stress, and low well-being related to the didactic and clinical challenges of their program, as well as external sources, including but not limited to relationship and financial strains (Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). According to Mesisca and Mainwaring's study of SRNAs in 2021, 67% of respondents demonstrated low well-being, which was associated with high levels of distress and unfavorable sequelae such as decreased quality of life, burnout, fatigue, suicidal ideation, and increased risk for dropping out. Additionally, chronically heightened stress levels have a detrimental impact on SRNA's academic performance, regardless of their seniority in the program (Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). Since provider well-being is crucial in the delivery of safe anesthesia, long-term stress diminishes this, leading to burnout which can negatively impact patient care (Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). Depersonalization, less focus on patient-centered care, errors, and adverse patient outcomes can occur as a result of decreased well-being, costing organizations up to \$75 billion per year (Han et al., 2019; Kendrick, 2000; Salyer et al., 2016).

Medical students encounter similar challenges; thus, medical schools have traditionally offered various forms of mentorship that assist in transitioning to a higher level of education and clinical practice (Akinla et al., 2018). Medical students receiving mentorship have lower reported stress, increased resilience, and less distress during transitional periods as their education advances (Akinla et al., 2018; Etzel et al., 2018; Nakhostin-Ansari et al., 2021). In medical students, mentorship has proven to significantly increase student tolerance to new or unfamiliar situations, which may lower stress and burnout (Nakhostin-Ansari et al., 2021).

While some nurse anesthesia programs have formal and informal faculty mentorship programs, students feel more comfortable seeking advice and guidance from near-peers or senior

students within medical schools (Laurence et al., 2020). Wake Forest School of Medicine utilizes a semi-structured student-led mentorship program that pairs fourth-year students with first-year students, providing real-time academic and emotional guidance from trained mentors (Laurence et al., 2020). The University of Texas San Antonio School of Medicine also offers a formal mentorship program where senior students support juniors through monthly group and one-on-one activities (Andre et al., 2017). This student-led program supplements faculty mentorship and assists in navigating medical school, career advising, and academic strategies (Andre et al., 2017). Despite the perceived benefits of mentorship, very little formal execution of or research on structured mentor programs for nurse anesthesia students occurs (Pallaria et al., 2021). Peer mentorship involves pairing a senior student who can provide professional, educational, and personal guidance and support to a newer student (Akinla et al., 2018). This student-to-student relationship demonstrates positive outcomes in undergraduate and graduate learning, leading to stress reduction with the transition into programs (Altonji et al., 2019). Peer mentorship has also demonstrated benefits for mentors, including increased confidence and the development of collaborative, leadership, and teaching skills (Andersen & Watkins, 2018).

Significance

In 2004, the American Association of Colleges of Nursing (AACN) published a position statement recommending the elevation of all advanced practice registered nurse (APRN) education to the doctoral level (AACN, 2004). Subsequently, in 2018, KPSA demonstrated its commitment to education by transitioning to a Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) degree (KPSA, 2022b). While this change elevates the profession of nurse anesthesia, it has a significant impact on individual students as the transition to doctoral programs increases the amount of coursework required, the cost of education, and the length of time SRNAs cannot earn an income.

Currently, the cost of attending KPSA's DNP program is estimated at \$92,000 for California residents, which does not include housing, transportation, or living expenses (KPSA, 2022a). The program is rigorous, with students taking 15 units in their first semester and 109 units with over 1,000 clinical hours over three years. Additionally, KPSA students face pressure to perform well academically, fearing program disqualification if they earn a grade below 83% (KPSA, 2022c). While KPSA has a low attrition rate of 6%, efforts to reduce the stress and anxiety SRNAs face should be aimed at sustainable interventions such as peer mentorship (KPSA, 2022d).

The various consequences of prolonged stress for SRNAs can lead to chronic health issues and attrition; conversely, mentorship can lead to the development of useful coping skills to reduce harmful reactions to stress and potentially increase productivity and learning (Conner, 2015; Farlow et al., 2021). A lack of mentorship opportunities and social support have been identified as potential contributors to student burnout and attrition (Champion et al., 2015). In a review of literature by Conner (2015), emphasis was placed on earlier emotional and academic support to counter stressors during certified registered nurse anesthetist (CRNA) school. By providing social support, self-efficacy, the belief that one can accomplish an objective can be enhanced, thereby promoting retention, success in the program, and creating better coping mechanisms (Conner, 2015).

Structured peer mentorship sessions may improve student comprehension of didactic topics when discussed (Farlow et al., 2021). Peer mentorship provides advice mentees find valuable, and mentees felt it eased transitionary periods during their education (Etzel et al., 2018; Farlow et al., 2021). Medical students who receive mentorship exhibit decreased stress and increased resilience and may have greater tolerance when facing novel situations, which can be

expected during periods of transition such as those from didactic to clinical training (Akinla et al., 2018; Nakhostin-Ansari et al., 2021). Mentorship reducing perceived stress or facilitating the transition into clinical rotations extends to other allied health professions outside of medical school (Etzel et al., 2018; Greene, 2021). Mentees may be more comfortable with near-peer mentors than faculty, and peer mentorship may have increased academic, social, and emotional benefits (Singh et al., 2014). There is a gap in research establishing the benefits of mentorship in SRNAs. Creating and implementing a formalized near-peer SRNA mentorship program at KPSA may provide significant value to students by decreasing stress, easing significant transitional periods, and may possibly result in increased academic performance.

Problem Statement

Student registered nurse anesthetists can experience significant anxiety and stress during their three years of doctoral education. As a result, SRNAs may display burnout and fatigue, resulting in program attrition, poor mental health and well-being, and suicidal ideation (Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). Current literature suggests that medical students and other allied health professionals receiving mentorship have decreased stress, increased resilience, and may experience fewer distressing periods of transition to didactic and clinical demands (Akinla et al., 2018; Etzel et al., 2018; Nakhostin-Ansari et al., 2021). Although the benefits of mentorship have been studied in the medical school student and physician resident population, a gap exists in research establishing the benefits of implementing evidence-based mentorship programs for SRNAs. Moreover, KPSA does not currently have a formalized student mentorship program.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project is to obtain baseline stress and mentorship satisfaction levels from current KPSA cohorts that can be used in conjunction with current literature to make recommendations for the future implementation of a formal mentorship program at KPSA.

Project Objectives

The objectives of this doctoral project are to:

- Assess students' overall satisfaction with their current mentorship
- Assess the effectiveness of the peer-mentorship currently offered at KPSA
- Identify common themes in student responses to reveal mentorship needs
- Obtain baseline perceived stress levels of students

This project will address gaps in research on SRNA mentorship and recommendations made will assist in creating a mentorship program and may serve as a framework to be used in the training and education of SRNAs. Future investigators must establish evaluation criteria and may utilize baseline and post-intervention assessments to determine whether program implementation meets expectations and leads to a reduction in overall stress levels for SRNAs.

Supporting Framework

Solutions to clinical practice issues must be guided by evidence, necessitating the evaluation and synthesis of research evidence to determine the most appropriate interventions. The Iowa Model of Research-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care, known as the Iowa Model, was developed by Marita Titler and staff nurses in 1994 at the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics (UIHC) (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The model is a step-by-step guideline for clinicians in evaluating and creating practice changes for patient care (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The Iowa Model continues to be utilized as an evidence-based practice (EBP) framework

due to its initiatives to align with organizational goals while emphasizing practice care issues that are significant for the staff and patients (Duff et al., 2020). With the evolution of EBP and the demands of healthcare changing, the Iowa Model has undergone multiple revisions, with the last one in 2017 (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The Iowa Model is one of the best-researched EBP models and it has been utilized to implement evidence-based change in the perioperative, labor and delivery, and oncology settings (McEwen & Wills, 2019). The redesigned Iowa Model (Appendix A) will provide a framework for this project. It will provide guidance on how to proceed in instituting and implementing a new mentorship program for future researchers.

Previous Use of the Iowa Model for Practice Change

The Iowa Model has been utilized in several studies to identify improvement opportunities and plan and implement evidence-based change. The Iowa Model was instrumental in successfully instituting evidence-based change to combat central line-associated bloodstream infection rates in the large tertiary care hospital setting (Beeler et al., 2019). Similarly, another quality improvement project identified a change opportunity triggered by high rates of catheter-associated urinary tract infections at a long-term care facility (Zurmehly, 2018). Utilizing the Iowa Model, research was conducted, a plan was developed and implemented, resulting in a decline in infection rates by 74%. The Iowa Model has been used successfully to facilitate large-scale changes, such as guiding the creation and institution of a fall risk assessment tool into the medication administration record (MAR) of twelve hospital systems across three states (McCarty et al., 2018). The step-by-step guidance and success of the Iowa Model across varied settings make it a sound framework for this project.

Identifying an Opportunity for Improvement and Stating a Purpose

In following the Iowa Model, step one of this project is to identify an issue or opportunity for improvement. According to KPSA faculty, with the transition of the nurse anesthesia program from a two-year master's program to a three-year doctoral program in 2018, there has been a marked increase in the level of stress and anxiety KPSA students have faced. This has been attributed to the additional time, coursework, and financial impact SRNAs encounter with a third year of study. Therefore, the purpose of this project, or step two of the Iowa Model, is to investigate whether the creation of an evidence-based peer-mentorship program at KPSA would support SRNAs by lowering SRNA stress and anxiety.

Priority

After identifying the purpose, the first of three decision points in the model appears (Appendix A), where it is determined whether SRNA peer-mentorship is a priority for KPSA. While factors contributing to SRNA anxiety and stress cannot be eliminated, efforts can be made to mitigate some of that stress and anxiety; therefore, KPSA has committed to exploring solutions to alleviate this issue among SRNAs. Among potential solutions, peer mentorship was identified as an option with a low financial burden and high impact. Stress and anxiety in KPSA students have not been measured directly, but faculty attest to witnessing these adverse effects and hope to align the school's actions with Kaiser Permanente's mission to support total health moving forward. Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia is committed to working toward a meaningful solution because this issue is related to program satisfaction and affects all SRNAs in the United States (US). Unresolved, the burden of chronic stress and anxiety can lead to burnout which would detrimentally affect the entire profession of nurse anesthetists (Champion et al., 2015).

Team Formation

Step three of the Iowa Model involves the formation of a team that is responsible for the development, implementation, and evaluation of the mentorship program. The team is composed of junior SRNAs, and two faculty team leads, one of which is a subject matter expert from the school of anesthesia. A new group of KPSA students will replace the current junior SRNAs in the implementation and evaluation phases of the proposed mentorship program. Key stakeholders include KPSA faculty and administration, KPSA students who will participate in the program as mentors and mentees, and potentially the California Association of Nurse Anesthetists (CANA) and American Association of Nurse Anesthetists (AANA) who are working at the state and national level to implement their own SRNA wellness initiatives.

Evidence Collection and Appraisal

After the team has been formed, step four involves assembling, appraising, and synthesizing literature. Research databases such as CINAHL, PubMed, and Cochrane resulted in 20 articles that met inclusion and exclusion criteria. Inclusion criteria consisted of articles that were peer-reviewed, English, and mentor programs encompassing professional health programs. Exclusion criteria included studies that focused on faculty mentors and student-teaching. The literature review focuses on stress in SRNAs, coping mechanisms, and sequelae, various forms of mentorship found in medical training programs, and near-peer mentorship.

After conducting a review of the literature, the second decision point, or stop, of the Iowa Model (Appendix A) involves grading the literature and making practice recommendations. The literature obtained included those with a level III or higher score on the Johns Hopkins Nurse Evidence-based Practice (JHNEBP) Rating Scale. Level III studies include non-experimental, quasi-experimental, and qualitative (Dang et al., 2022). The lack of available evidence on SRNA

peer mentorship in the literature suggests more studies in the SRNA population are warranted; however, there is a significant amount of research on the topic in medical students and very similar student populations allowing us to generalize the results and make evidence-based recommendations in favor of mentorship programs. The literature supports the creation and use of a mentorship program due to the positive outcomes in SRNAs, most notably decreased stress and improved experience with transitioning into higher levels of education and academic success. Additionally, the studies revealed potential barriers, such as scheduling issues, that will require consideration when creating a mentorship program.

Pilot Test of Change

The fifth step moving forward using the Iowa Model is to design a pilot test of change which allows the team to evaluate if the instituted change is adopted and has the desired outcome (Cullen et al., 2018). An evidence-based protocol that is specific to the setting should be developed, with implementation strategies based on gathered baseline data (Cullen et al., 2018).

This project will collect baseline data and make recommendations for designing an evidence based SRNA mentorship program pilot to be implemented in the future. Baseline data will comprise a pre-intervention survey of students' stress measured by a validated standardized tool, the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) (Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). The survey will also contain additional free-response questions to reveal themes among students regarding topics or areas that would benefit from additional mentor guidance. Points of discussion and program highlights will be recommended based on themes revealed by data collected. Future post-pilot evaluation should utilize the same surveys used prior to intervention. Post-pilot questionnaires may contain additional free-response questions to evaluate students' satisfaction with the new mentorship program and identify barriers.

Appropriateness for Adoption

After pilot implementation, a stop is integrated into the Iowa Model (Appendix A) to assess the appropriateness of the change for adoption (Cullen et al., 2018). This project will collect the baseline pre-pilot data necessary for future pilot program evaluation. The appropriateness of the change for adoption will depend on post-pilot outcome measures, which either endorse the practice change for adoption or necessitate pilot redesign or collection of further evidence (Cullen et al., 2018).

Integrating and Sustaining the Practice Change

The sixth step of the Iowa Model is integrating and sustaining the adopted change (Cullen et al., 2018). This project plans to provide the foundational basis to begin a sustainable adopted formalized mentorship program at KPSA. Our planned pilot includes buy-in from KPSA leadership, which is vital to sustainability. This will come in the form of school-led training initiatives and policy changes to reflect the implementation of the mentorship program, as well as protected mentorship time. A student-led committee of volunteers from each cohort could be formed and meet as often as necessary to communicate real-time feedback to KPSA faculty to sustain the change further. Additionally, a third-year student with mentoring experience may fill the role of senior mentor as an additional resource to mentors and mentees.

Dissemination

The last step of the Iowa Model is the dissemination of the results of the practice change. Internal dissemination of the results of this project will take place at California State University Fullerton in 2023. External dissemination will take place at other locations to be determined in the future. Pre-prepared oral presentations with visual aids in the form of electronic presentation slides and posters will be used to facilitate the dissemination of results. Lastly, there is the

potential for dissemination at the state and national level at CANA and AANA conferences after program evaluation.

Conclusion

The Iowa Model will help provide guidance in the creation of a peer mentorship program via seven steps. Using a knowledge deficit and problem-based trigger, the model may assist in evidence-based recommendations that will ultimately be used by future researchers to create and pilot a program.

Review of Literature

Overview

A literature review was conducted to evaluate manifestations and consequences of stress in SRNAs with an emphasis placed on investigating the various methods of student mentorship. The review of literature also discusses background information on how different forms of student mentorship in professional health education and training programs affect learners. The literature review was conducted using the research databases PubMed, Cochrane, and CINAHL. The following keywords were used in the search: *student nurse anesthetist, student nurse, nurse, near-peer, mentor, peer mentor, mentoring, mentorship, preceptorship, coaching, clinical competency, medical school, healthcare, nursing, medical student, SRNA, and CRNA*. MeSH terms included: *mentorship, preceptorship, clinical competency, nurse, student, and nurse anesthetist*. Inclusion criteria included peer-reviewed articles, English language, and mentor programs for professional health programs including nursing, speech pathology, medical school, and pharmacy school. Literature included a score of level III or higher based on the JHNEBP Rating Scale (Dang et al., 2022). On the JHNEBP Rating Scale, level I evidence contains randomized control trials (RCT) and systematic reviews of only RCT. Level II contains quasi-experimental studies and systematic reviews that include quasi-experimental studies. Non-experimental studies, such as qualitative studies and systematic reviews that contain them, are assigned to level III. Level IV evidence includes the opinions of respected authorities and expert committees based on scientific evidence such as practice guidelines. Level V evidence is experiential and non-research evidence, such as case reports and opinions based on experimental evidence.

Time restrictions were not utilized to allow for earlier studies to be accessed. Exclusion criteria included articles only utilizing faculty or professional mentors and studies that employed student-led instruction as the sole form of mentorship. Twenty articles met the inclusion criteria; two were randomized control trials coming from the level I category of the JHNEBP Rating scale. From level II, there were eight quasi-experimental studies included. Additionally, nine non-experimental studies and one systematic review that included non-experimental studies were included as level III evidence.

Effects of Peer Mentorship

The literature review identified four primary constructs to demonstrate the effects of peer mentorship on SRNAs. Evidence from the four constructs, stress, coping mechanisms and outcomes, mentorship in medical training and healthcare training, and lastly, near peer variations of mentorship has been synthesized and is presented in this paper.

Stressors in Student Registered Nurse Anesthetists

While stress may serve as motivation to succeed in one's goals, it exists on a continuum and prolonged exposure may result in untoward consequences (Conner, 2015; Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). In transitioning back into the student role, mental preparation is of utmost importance (Hughes, 2020). Upon acceptance into the program, SRNAs must face financial loss with full-time study, residing in a new location, time limitations, intensive coursework, and potential relationship strains (Conner, 2015; Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). Incoming students typically have an established career and family life, which must be placed on hold at the start of their program (Hughes, 2020). Furthermore, a potential source of increased stress is due to the limitations on time, resulting in SRNAs being unable to spend time with their social support systems (Conner, 2015).

While having to adjust to the challenges of lifestyle changes, students are expected to excel in the academic and clinical arenas as well. Students must be able to critically think in a technologically complex environment while in the operating room in addition to managing an abundance of information in the classroom setting (Conner, 2015). While the operating room is the most valuable environment for SRNAs to learn, the constant pressure of patient throughput and operating room turnover limits the depth of guidance and learning possible while also imparting a sense of chaos in SRNAs (Averlind & Hoglund, 2020). They are tasked with higher levels of autonomy than what they experienced as nurses and are ultimately responsible for making life-and-death decisions (Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). An additional stressor for SRNAs during clinicals is navigating the relationship with their preceptors and the lack of support, especially with the switch from a master's to a doctoral degree (Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). The transition from a master's to a doctoral program has been shown to add to the stress for SRNAs, due to an increased workload that is oftentimes unrelated to their focus on anesthesia (Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). Based on a review of current and historic literature on the subject, it is evident that stress is derived from a variety of sources and impacts the SRNA mentally and physically. Therefore, efforts must be made to mitigate stress and ensure SRNAs have the support and resources necessary to cope effectively.

Stress Symptoms

Recurrent stress for SRNAs can manifest as mental health crises, sleep disturbances, suicidal ideation, fatigue, gastrointestinal symptoms, drug and alcohol abuse, and declining academic performance (Downey et al., 2017; Johnson, 2018; Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). While these effects are quite typical of advanced healthcare education and training programs, issues arise when stress is experienced over long periods of time making it and the complications

that accompany it chronic. In their investigation of stress in anesthesia trainees by Downey et al. (2017), 11% of SRNAs were currently being treated for anxiety or depression and there was high psychological distress in 28% of respondents suggesting that there was a greater incidence of affective disorders and anxiety. Although not statistically significant, a cross-sectional study showed that 10% of the SRNAs had thoughts of death or suicide (Johnson, 2018).

Fatigue and irritability are also affected in that as SRNAs experience elevated levels of distress, they report having inadequate sleep and increased irritability (Downey et al., 2017; Johnson, 2018). Downey et al. (2017) found a statistically significant correlation between high or very high Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K10) scores and inadequate sleep ($p = 0.005$), suggesting that with more distress during the program, anesthesia trainees were likely to have less sleep. In another study, students stated that they medically managed their inability to sleep with herbal supplements, melatonin, benzodiazepines, Benadryl, alcohol, and marijuana (Johnson, 2018). As stress starts to affect restfulness, SRNAs are forced to utilize coping mechanisms that involve substance abuse and may have psychological implications later in their lives and careers.

Gastrointestinal issues such as increased inflammation and appetite changes also arise from stress (Yaribeygi et al., 2017). Stress alters the physiology of the intestines and stomach leading to increased risks of irritable bowel, ulcerative colitis, and Crohn's disease (Yaribeygi et al., 2017). Digestive issues such as heartburn or gastroesophageal reflux disease were found in 35.29% of SRNA respondents in prior studies (Hughes, 2020). Doctoral students have a higher incidence of digestive disorders than master's students, although not statistically significant (Johnson, 2018). As seen in the symptomology discussed previously, the results of stress have negative consequences when it comes to one's health and well-being.

Stress and Academic Performance

Stress may negatively impact SRNA's academic performance and there is constant worry about being dismissed from their program (Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). In addition to physiological and emotional strain, SRNAs also deal with ongoing performance assessments and the risk of errors in the clinical setting (Downey et al., 2017). Student registered nurse anesthetists worry about having "blackouts" when practicing independently and not knowing how to act in emergency situations (Averlid & Hoglund, 2020). Students with increasing anxiety and stress had low well-being and reported a perceived negative effect academically, identifying that studying for exams was the greatest source of stress (Downey et al., 2017; Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). Chronic stress is detrimental to memory, learning, judgment, and may even lead to atrophy of the brain (Yaribeygi et al., 2017). In addition, the impact of stress during DNP programs often led to feelings of confusion as one of the top symptoms noted (Johnson, 2018). These findings suggest that stress is constant and adversely influences academic and clinical performance. Repeated exposure to stress may lead to long-term consequences in one's mental clarity and brain function.

Stress Management and Coping

Stress in SRNAs has a profound impact on their mental health and results in poor coping mechanisms. Research has shown that high stress levels in SRNAs is associated with anxiety, depression, and poor quality of life (Downey et al., 2017; Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). Among the coping mechanisms noted throughout the literature is the overconsumption of alcohol which can continue as a practicing CRNA after completing school (Downey et al., 2017; Johnson, 2018). The risk of recreational drug use is also noted in SRNAs, however, not as prevalent as alcohol use (Downey et al., 2017). Due to the excessive workload and time limitations, SRNAs

adopt unhealthy lifestyle practices such as lack of self-care or exercise, and poor diet leading to an increased risk of obesity (Downey et al., 2017; Johnson, 2018). These findings suggest that stress has physiological manifestations and without proper resources or preparatory stress management, can harm the SRNA's well-being.

Recommendations for Improvement in Academic Programs

One common theme that has emerged from this review of stress in SRNAs is the need for intervention in the early stages of training. Promotion of wellness, work-life balance, self-care, and support from faculty and peers should be a priority to prevent negative consequences (Downey et al., 2017; Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). Among the suggestions to improve SRNA's quality of life, mentorship is commonly referred to as a solution. Formal meetings with a mentor were done only 34% of the time, potentially due to either party's lack of availability, issues with communication, or lack of interest (Downey et al., 2017). In addition, SRNAs have identified that a mentorship program integrated into the curriculum may help with guidance and support for students (Downey et al., 2017; Johnson, 2018). Advocating for a culture of support and incorporating wellness among SRNAs is vital to their growth and success while in school (Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). The lack of mentorship for SRNAs, whether formal or informal, is evident in the literature, and implementation can serve as an adjunct to managing daily stressors and assist in navigating through a rigorous program.

Mentorship in Medical Students

Mentorship has been utilized and studied extensively in the medical student population. A near-peer mentorship program created by Farlow et al. (2021) for medical students demonstrated a quantitative increase in pre-test and post-test performance on two of three clinical topics covered. Additionally, mentees reported in qualitative questionnaires that

interaction with resident mentors and advice regarding the transition to residency were the most valuable aspects of the program. A RCT conducted by Senjovu et al. (2021) involving 1:1 peer-mentorship for the intervention group demonstrated increased clinical knowledge and competency scores for up to one year. As measured by the Budner Ambiguity Tolerance Scale, lower ambiguity tolerance is associated with anxiety, stress, burnout, and mental health issues (Nakhostin-Ansari et al., 2021). Medical students with a mentor had a statistically significantly higher novelty subscale than students without a mentor. The authors interpret the findings to mean that mentored students may have increased resilience to new, unfamiliar situations, such as the transition to the clinical environment (Nakhostin-Ansari et al., 2021). A systematic review of first-year medical students in near-peer mentoring programs suggests peer mentorship decreased student stress, increased resilience, and lessened the difficulty of transition into medical school (Akinla et al., 2018). While the results were positive, the review was limited to only five studies of varying quality and stress levels were not measured quantitatively; therefore, these results may not be reproducible (Akinla et al., 2018).

Mentorship in Other Health Professions

Given the gap in research on SRNA mentorship, literature related to mentorship in healthcare professionals other than medical students and residents was reviewed to identify any inferences that could be applicable. The following studies demonstrated the benefits of mentorship in a variety of healthcare professional education programs. A mixed-method pilot study of a peer mentorship program administered to 23 undergraduate nurses by Wang et al. (2022) showed a decline in mean Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale scores. While their findings were not statistically significant, likely due to the small sample size; qualitatively, mentored undergraduate nurses reported increased mental well-being and personal and

professional growth due to mentorship (Wang et al., 2022). A randomized control trial of peer mentorship in 10 first-year speech-language pathology students compared to 10 in a control group found a statistically significant reduction in stress as measured by the PSS in mentored students compared to control (Greene, 2021). A quasi-experimental study of $n = 289$ pharmacy students conducted by Etzel et al. (2018) found that mentored students reported less stress, especially during the transitional period of beginning the program for first-year pharmacy students. However, mentorship was not found to impact student attrition rates. The benefits of peer mentoring in nurse-midwifery students were investigated in a non-experimental study by Hogan et al. in 2017. One hundred and six enrolled mentees were surveyed yearly for three years. Qualitative analysis revealed themes suggesting mentor advice reduced the anxiety of clinical rotations and provided reassurance and support building confidence (Hogan et al., 2017).

Near-Peer Mentoring Variations

Near-peer mentoring is specified as a learner who is at least one year senior to another learner providing guidance and support throughout the course of higher education which can be extremely stressful (Akinla et al., 2018). This form of mentorship has a variety of other names such as vertical peer-mentoring (Andre et al., 2017) and step-ahead mentoring (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, & Medicine (NASEM), 2019). Regardless of the name, the premise of students helping students remains at the foundation of each study included in this literature review. This relationship differs from faculty or professional mentorships in that near-peer mentors have more insight into the day-to-day issues mentees face and can offer real-time support (Laurence et al., 2020).

Mentorship typically occurs in dyads, meaning one mentor is paired with one mentee; however, triads and mentoring groups are also feasible (NASEM, 2019). Farlow et al. (2021)

describe an online near-peer mentorship program in which a group of two to three otolaryngology residents met in an online forum with up to 10 fourth-year medical students from across the country. While scheduling difficulties between mentor and mentee were highlighted as a significant barrier, overall, mentees reported benefiting from the guidance received and contact with residents. Laurence et al. (2020) describes an optional pilot program in which a fourth-year medical student served as a 'guide' for two first-year medical students or 'guidees'. The program was formal in that guides were provided with mentor skills training, meeting outlines to direct conversations with guidees, and a formal matching process (Laurence et al., 2020). A large number of guidees assigned to one guide made it difficult to coordinate schedules, and some guidees were hesitant to initiate contact out of fear of being bothersome (Laurence et al., 2020). Similarly, Hogan et al. (2017) created a peer-mentorship program for first-year midwifery students who did not have a background in healthcare. In contrast to other studies, only the mentor training was thoroughly described and formalized. The mentor-mentee relationship was informal and non-structured, and mentees were noted to be non-proactive in seeking help from mentors (Hogan et al., 2017). A study by Singh et al. (2014) successfully utilized near-peer mentoring as an adjunct to faculty mentoring for first-year medical students. Groups consisted of one faculty mentor, one near-peer mentor, and two to three mentees. In these groups, students utilized near-peer mentors significantly more than faculty mentors (Singh et al., 2014). Despite the variations in program structure, the majority of participants felt they benefited from near-peer mentorship (Farlow et al., 2021; Laurence et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2014).

The Impact of Mentorship in the Clinical Setting

Literature review did not identify recent literature on the impact of the transition to clinical and clinical performance in SRNAs or newly graduated CRNAs. However, literature on

mentorship and its implications on clinical knowledge, performance, or ease of transition were found for newly graduated registered nurses and advanced practice nurses.

Transition to Clinical and Clinical Confidence

In 2022, Nolan et al. published an integrative literature review to investigate which elements of mentorship or preceptorship facilitated the successful transition of new nurse midwives to clinical practice. Mentorship and preceptorship were used synonymously in the literature. They reviewed 316 papers between 1990 and 2021, 10 of which met inclusion criteria. The authors cited burnout, stress, anxiety, and depression as factors influencing new midwives to leave the profession early in their careers (Nolan et al., 2022). The authors concluded that preceptorship by experienced midwives was essential in increasing the confidence of new midwives transitioning from student to professional roles (Nolan et al., 2022). Additional factors in successful programs were investment and integration from the organization, protected time for mentorship or education, and staffing necessary to facilitate available mentors. Scheduling between mentors and mentees was a noted barrier (Nolan et al., 2020). Online learning modules incorporated in some preceptorship programs helped develop clinical skills and confidence; protected time to complete these modules and interaction with mentors for support impacted the successful completion of modules (Nolan et al., 2022). Significant limitations included a lack of validated tools to measure the outcome in any of the included studies (Nolan et al., 2022). The quality and study methodology of the included literature also varied greatly.

Austin and Haplin (2021) studied mentorship and its impact on the transition shock of newly graduated pediatric nurses in a London hospital. Austin and Halpin (2021) conducted a small qualitative study of 10 nurses using structured interviews with prompting, which were analyzed for themes. One of the main themes identified was support and reassurance of the

transition process to the clinical setting, in which low confidence, anxiety, and feeling overwhelmed were reported (Austin & Haplin, 2021). Mentees found mentorship beneficial and reassuring, and the authors suggest it helped mentees work through these feelings with their mentor rather than having them linger in isolation (Austin & Haplin, 2021). Areas for improvement included having mentors establish contact with mentees and protected pre-scheduled meeting times to alleviate scheduling difficulties (Austin & Haplin, 2021). Clinical performance or knowledge was not investigated in this study. Mentorship is beneficial in the transition to clinical practice in that it assists nurses with uncertainty, increasing their confidence, and reduces emotional stressors.

Mentorship and Increased Clinical Competency

Chen et al. (2021) performed a cross-sectional descriptive study on the relationship between transition shock of newly graduated nurses, preceptor support, and nurse competency in China. The training and preceptorship period of the 215 new graduate nurses ranged from two weeks to one month. Competency was measured via self-report by new graduate nurses using a 53-item 5-point Likert scale tool with an overall Cronbach's alpha of 0.91 (Chen et al., 2021). Chen et al. (2021) found a statistically significant correlation between higher mean nursing competency scores and new graduate nurses' positive experience with preceptors, level of preceptor activity, and preceptor context. The preceptor context in this study encompasses the quality, availability, and organizational support provided to preceptors in their roles. Furthermore, the authors suggested an increased benefit from consistent one-on-one preceptorship with the same preceptor throughout training (Chen et al., 2021).

Senjouv et al. (2021) conducted a RCT of clinical mentorship of mid-level health providers managing tuberculosis (TB) and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) in Uganda.

Mid-level providers were described as clinical officers, registered nurses, and midwives taking on care previously provided by physicians. The intervention arm received eight hours of one-on-one clinical mentorship by a randomly assigned mentor every six weeks for nine months. The study had a follow-up period of one year after the intervention, and a combination of testing via clinical vignettes mimicking HIV and TB patient visits and standardized clinical observations were used to assess knowledge and clinical competence. The study displayed that the intervention group's mean knowledge and competency scores significantly improved compared to control (Senjouv et al., 2021). Although the control arm also saw some increase in knowledge and competency, the intervention arm achieved and maintained higher mean scores, which were achieved at an increased rate compared to the control (Senjouv et al., 2021). Participants in the intervention arm also reported in post-mentoring feedback that mentoring improved their confidence in managing HIV and TB cases (Senjouv et al., 2021). Limitations include a small sample size of 39, with 19 in the intervention group, and the rural nature of the Ugandan health care facility limiting generalizability to urban settings.

Goyet et al. (2020) conducted a prospective cross-sectional cohort study of 308 nurses enrolled in a clinical mentoring program to improve emergency obstetrical and newborn care. The study occurred at multiple emergency obstetric newborn care centers and birthing centers in Nepal and assessed nurses' knowledge and skills pre- and post-intervention. All nurses received one to three mentoring sessions covering 12 maternal and newborn care topics. The proportion of mentees who obtained knowledge assessment scores of $> 85\%$ increased by 28.3% ($p < 0.001$) as assessed by written tests (Goyet et al., 2020). Assessment of clinical ability also increased by 62.7% ($p < 0.001$), measured by the proportion of pre-defined standards of care met for a wide variety of clinical competencies (Goyet et al., 2020). Competencies included simple tasks such as

correctly decontaminating medical equipment or using sterile gloves to complex management of eclampsia, postpartum hemorrhagic shock, and newborn resuscitation.

Implications of Mentorship on Student Nurse Anesthetists in the Clinical Setting

The literature reviewed on mentorship and clinical implications did not include student nurse anesthetists and took place in various settings, mainly outside the US. As a result, this limits generalizability to the impact of mentorship in the clinical setting on SRNAs in the US. The review of literature on preceptorship in nurse midwives by Nolan et al. in 2022 and the qualitative study in pediatric nurses by Austin and Haplin (2021) suggest mentorship may help ease the transition to the clinical setting in inexperienced nurses and increase clinical confidence. Furthermore, nurses who received structured clinical mentorship had measurable increases in clinical knowledge and competence (Chen et al., 2021; Goyet et al., 2020; Senjouy et al., 2021). Therefore, a possible benefit of mentorship of SRNAs is the ease of transition to the clinical setting, increased confidence, and measurable gains in clinical knowledge and competency.

Methods

The purpose of this project is to provide evidence-based recommendations for a lasting and impactful peer mentorship program at KPSA that fosters collaboration and lowers stress among SRNAs. The aims of this project are to assess student satisfaction with current mentorship offered by KPSA, the effectiveness of that mentorship, identify common themes in responses to reveal student identified needs with regards to SRNA mentorship, and examine baseline perceived stress for three anesthesia cohorts. The three cohorts consist of approximately 90 total students, with roughly 30 students in each of the first, second, and third-year student cohorts. Analysis of the aforementioned assessments enabled the team to provide strong recommendations for the outline of a peer-mentorship program to be implemented at the school of anesthesia. This methods and evaluation section will outline design, setting, participants, ethical considerations, procedure, measures, data analysis, and evaluation.

Design

This project outlines the foundations for the development of a peer mentorship program utilizing a cross-sectional design; a single electronic survey will be used to establish baseline needs and provide recommendations for the creation of an evidence-based formalized peer mentorship program. The benefits of a cross-sectional design include examining multiple variables at a particular time, cost-effectiveness, ease, and the ability to utilize the findings to create hypotheses or to assist in furthering research studies (Wang & Cheng, 2020). Conversely, the limitations of a cross-sectional design using questionnaires include a low response rate and the inability to make causal inferences (Wang & Cheng, 2020). Pretest questionnaires will help establish a baseline student satisfaction and effectiveness of the current mentorship program and

perceived stress, which will assist in tracking any changes in these variables after implementing a peer mentorship program.

Setting

This project took place at a doctoral-level nurse anesthesia program in Pasadena, California via online surveys distributed to current SRNAs. The school was established in 1972 and has educated half of all CRNAs in California. Seven full-time faculty members from the school of anesthesia along with occasional guest lecturers educate all SRNAs in collaboration with a California State University doctoral nursing faculty over the duration of nine semesters. The program's first year focuses on didactic education and simulation training, followed by two years of clinical beginning in the fall of the second year. Didactic education continues throughout the remainder of the program in tandem with clinical rotations. The first two clinical rotations for general anesthesia practice total five months, after which SRNAs rotate to different specialty clinical sites monthly throughout the second year. The third year consists of three clinical rotations, each two to three months in duration. Historically, students are assigned a faculty member as a mentor with sporadic informal group meetings and one-on-one by student request. Students are also provided with the contact information of a peer the cohort ahead of them to serve as an informal mentor. The current mentorship initiatives are informal, and, per faculty, they are not enough to alleviate SRNA stress and anxiety.

Sample and Participants

The participants involved in this project included a convenience sample of current SRNAs at the school of anesthesia. There are three cohorts attending the school of anesthesia at any given time, each of which has approximately 30 students. Enrolled students must have a minimum of a bachelor's degree in nursing, greater than one year of full-time clinical registered

nursing experience in an adult critical care unit in the US, and a critical care registered nurse certification. Inclusion criteria is simply all SRNAs enrolled at this school of anesthesia; thus, for all three cohorts, approximately 90 students were expected to participate. Exclusion criteria are all non-nurse anesthesia students (i.e., anesthesia technicians) at this school, students not enrolled at this school of anesthesia, or those that are lost to attrition. There were no incentives offered for participation. Forty-seven students responded to the survey, ranging in age from 18-44, with 42 respondents being 25-34 years old. Respondents included 28 females and 19 males, 24 of whom reported being single or never married, and 23 were married or in a domestic partnership. Forty-four respondents reported being full-time students or unemployed, while three students work part-time. Twelve respondents reported being first-generation college students. Four students reported having one or more children, while 43 had no children.

Ethical Considerations

Institutional review board approval (IRB) was obtained from both KPSA and California State University, Fullerton (Appendix B). Participants were given an informed consent form that required agreement to receive the survey, which disclosed both the risks and benefits of participation, emphasizing that involvement in the study was entirely voluntary. In addition, participants were reassured that they have the right to withdraw from the project at any time and that they can omit answers to any of the survey questions. Anonymity was maintained by de-identifying the data obtained via the e-survey. Moreover, data was encrypted and saved on password protected devices that were double authenticated and only accessible to student researchers.

Procedure

Upon receiving IRB approval, the entire school of anesthesia's student body was initially notified of the project via email by the team lead. Subsequently, the student researchers sent electronic correspondence introducing themselves, the project purpose and aims, and inviting all DNP students to participate in the survey. Students were informed that while there were no monetary incentives for participation, this would be their opportunity to help tailor the program to their needs. For those who agreed to participate, baseline assessments of mentorship satisfaction, mentorship effectiveness, student-identified areas in need of additional mentorship, and baseline stress were collected. An email link to electronic versions of the PSS, Mentor Evaluation Tool (MET), and three open response questions were sent for this purpose. These assessments were de-identified to maintain confidentiality. During the two-month data collection period, two additional reminders were also emailed to ensure adequate responses were received.

Measures

The three-part surveys were electronically distributed to the convenience sample of the student body attending the school of anesthesia ($n = 90$). The first section of the survey assessed SRNA satisfaction levels with and effectiveness of currently offered informal mentorship. These were obtained quantitatively using the MET (Figure C1), a Likert scale questionnaire developed and validated by UCSF researchers (Yukawa et al., 2020). Baseline data on SRNA stress levels was obtained using the PSS (Figure C2), a validated research tool that assisted in ascertaining individual stress levels (Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). This baseline data may be utilized by future student researchers in evaluating various stages of the project's implementation and evaluation. The final portion of the survey comprised the mentorship needs assessment in which qualitative data was obtained from open-ended questions (Figure C3) where SRNAs can suggest

areas for mentorship improvement and identify topics or areas that would benefit from additional mentorship. While the literature supports peer-mentorship, the results of the needs assessment will help guide the SRNA peer-mentorship program's development.

Mentor Evaluation Tool

The MET (Figure C1) was created by UCSF researchers and validated in large-scale studies among graduate students in 2010 and 2014. This tool assesses the effectiveness of one-on-one mentoring in health science academics. It has been used previously in nursing, medical, dental, and pharmacy graduate programs and is administered to mentees (Yukawa et al., 2020). The MET is a 13-item, seven-point Likert scale survey with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.94 (Yukawa et al., 2020). The MET provides a way to study mentoring further and involves examining mentor characteristics, mentee preferences, and the effectiveness of mentoring training programs. This tool has flexibility not previously found in other instruments and should become a valuable resource as more institutions develop mentoring programs (Yukawa et al., 2020).

Perceived Stress Scale

The PSS questionnaire (Figure C2) is a validated and reliable tool consisting of a 10-item, five-point Likert scale to obtain baseline perceived stress. Higher scores on the PSS indicate higher levels of perceived stress, with lower scores indicating lower perceived stress. Scores can range from 0-40, and low stress levels include scores from 0-13, moderate stress levels are defined as 14-26, and high levels of stress include scores from 27-40 (New Hampshire Department of Administrative Services, 2023). The PSS has a Cronbach's α consistently above 0.7, and has been used in student populations (Lee, 2012; Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021).

Thematic Analysis of Open Response Questions

The survey contained open-response questions related to student-identified mentorship needs and suggestions for improving the mentorship program (Figure C3). Participant responses were coded to reveal common themes that identify student needs and recommendations to be addressed by a future mentorship program.

Data Collection

Data was collected through an anonymous online survey distributed via email to all students via Qualtrics. Demographic data was collected, including age, gender, race, marital status, previous level of education, and first-generation college student status. Additional demographics collected include years in the program and years of experience as an intensive care unit (ICU) nurse before attending anesthesia school. Surveys contain three parts: the MET, a needs assessment in the form of free-response questions, and the PSS. These surveys were collected over two months, from May 2023 to July 2023, prior to the initiation of any formal mentorship program to collect baseline data. De-identified electronic survey information was collected and stored on encrypted password-protected computers.

Results

The results were quantitative and qualitative in nature. Statistical analysis was performed on survey data collected on demographics, PSS scores, and MET scores. Thematic analysis was employed to evaluate written responses to the three open-ended survey questions (Figure C3).

Quantitative Results

Forty-seven of the 90 students invited participated in the survey, with 22.7% of the respondents from the class of 2023, 50% from the class of 2024, and 27.3% from the class of 2025 (Appendix D). Female participants outnumbered males at 60%; male respondents were 40%. The age group with the highest responses was Age Group 2 (25-34 years), with a total of 89.4%. Age Group 1 (18-24 years) had only one response, and Age Group 3 (35-44 years) had four responses, which was 8.5%. Most participants had three to five years of ICU experience ($n = 29$), followed by five to seven years of experience ($n = 12$), one to two years ($n = 4$), and seven to nine years ($n = 2$). The income variable was largely represented by an income less than \$25,000 ($n = 22$), whereas an income of \$50,000-\$75,000 was least represented ($n = 1$).

Overall, 57% of the respondents from the school of anesthesia demonstrated moderate levels of stress based on their PSS scores, and 6% demonstrated high levels of stress. Alone, it was clear that the class of 2024 had the most representation in the moderate stress category (mean PSS score = 20), and the class of 2025 made up the majority of the low-stress level scores (mean PSS score = 12).

When analyzing the PSS scores based on demographic variables, the highest stress level came from the 18-24 age group, which only had only one respondent who scored 26 on the PSS, indicating a moderate to high stress level. Meanwhile, the 26-34 and 35-44 age groups both had an average PSS score of 17, indicating moderate stress. When taking into account income, the

group that earned less than \$25,000 had the most representation and an average PSS score of 17. Income brackets \$25,001 to \$50,000 and \$50,001 to \$75,000 had high PSS averages of 23 and 24, respectively. For the middle to high-income brackets, \$75,001 to above \$150,000, the average PSS was 13 (18 total responses). The lowest PSS scores came from income group 5, \$100,000-149,000, with an average PSS of 10. Forty-three respondents indicated their employment status was “full-time student,” while four reported working part-time or looking for work. The average PSS score of the small group still working or looking for work was 21.5, with three of the four individuals scoring 26 on the PSS, indicating moderate to high stress levels. Females had a higher average PSS score of 18.5 compared to males, who had an average of 15.

Spearman correlation was utilized to explore the relationship between demographic variables that are ordinal or ranked. When one variable increases, there is an increase in another variable, which is indicative of a positive correlation; likewise, a negative correlation is when one variable increases, the other decreases (Pallant, 2010). A positive correlation was found between mean MET scores and employment ($r = 0.264$) and higher levels of parental education ($r = 0.130$). There was a negative correlation between PSS score and higher levels of employment ($r = -0.208$), higher levels of parental education ($r = -0.373$), and mean MET scores ($r = -0.328$).

Linear regression analysis allows us to explore the predictive ability of the perceived stress levels based on a set of independent variables, such as employment status, mentorship satisfaction, age, income, and parental education (Pallant, 2010). Based on these variables, the linear regression analysis shows that 25% of the variability in the PSS score can be explained by the model $R^2 = 0.025$ and p -value = 0.0360, indicating that the model is statistically significant at

the 5% level (Pallant, 2010). Among our variables, only two showed statistical significance: parental education ($p = 0.044$) and mean MET ($p = 0.010$).

Qualitative Results

Surveys contained three free-response questions to analyze student experiences regarding mentorship needs and areas for mentorship program improvement (Figure C3). Of the 47 respondents, 16 did not answer free-response questions, with 31 student responses remaining for thematic analysis. Responses were coded by the authors using NVivo R1, version 1.17.1. Wherever individual authors applied differing codes, coded responses were discussed until coding and interpretation were unanimous. Responses were reviewed and coded until saturation was achieved with no new emerging codes. The coding of survey responses generated 99 coded instances belonging to 28 unique codes. Upon thematic analysis of coded data, repeated patterns emerged in surveyed students' experiences. Two main themes emerged after analysis, *Resilience Seeking* and *Mentorship Formalization*, each with two sub-themes (Appendix E).

Resilience Seeking

Students repeatedly expressed seeking more support, advice, resources, or strategies from their mentors to overcome the stressors and challenges of anesthesia school. Responses indicated that students look to mentors for additional resilience to meet specific challenges they face as students, which their near-peer mentors have previously navigated. The need for this support forms one of the two primary themes: *Resilience Seeking*. Within the theme of *Resilience Seeking*, commonalities were found in participants' responses, highlighting the student experiences for which they seek guidance and thus, resilience, from their mentors. These commonalities were distinct in the type of aid they wanted from mentors, and from these coded

responses, two sub-themes emerged under the primary theme of *Resilience Seeking*. These sub-themes are *Milestone Guidance* and *Support of Wellbeing* (Appendix E).

Milestone Guidance

The sub-theme *Milestone Guidance* encompasses the students' desire to be able to turn to mentors for additional resources to bolster them during specific occasions in their development as student nurse anesthetists. These distinct events are milestones in their progression that reflect major student stressors. When traversing these milestones, participants seek bolstering from mentors during both regular occurrences, such as examinations, to distinct novel events in their development, as indicated by student responses such as “[Mentorship in] transitions from didactic to clinical realms of anesthesia.”

These instances of milestone guidance also span the entire continuum of their time in the anesthesia program, from seeking to adopt more successful study strategies for exams early on to refining their clinical and academic abilities as they progress. Student responses indicate this extends to finding employment at the end of the program, “Next I’m looking to what facilities I want to work at... so mentorship on the culture, benefits, schedules, and environments of various clinical sites would be helpful”, wrote one participant.

Support of Well-being

The second sub-theme under *Resilience Seeking* emerged from coded responses that are categorically different from the stressors encompassed by *Milestone Guidance* in that they are continuous stressors divorced from specific events. Students indicate wanting to seek further mentor support for stressors such as stress and time management, school-life balance, navigating financial burdens, and emotional support, stated succinctly by one student as the “stress of school on mental health.” These specific, continuous, more intangible needs described by respondents

comprise the *Resilience Seeking* sub-theme of *Support of Well-being*. These stressors are less tangible than those addressed by *Milestone Guidance*, in which mentees often report soliciting specific resources or strategies to strengthen them against stress. In contrast, some respondents expressly seek reassurance or empathy when desiring more *Support of Well-being* from mentors.

Mentorship Formalization

Another prominent theme emerged from the thematic analysis of survey responses regarding improving the mentorship program as a whole. Respondents explicitly and repeatedly indicate the need for a more structured, organized, formal near-peer mentorship compared to the informal mentorship currently employed by their nurse anesthesia program. The theme of *Mentorship Formalization* encapsulates these student experiences. Student responses express differing aspects they feel are essential to formalize within the mentorship program. Their desires range from broad statements indicating the need for more structure to the program to specifics such as mentor matching, scheduled meetings, defined mentor-mentee roles, and social events. Within these aspects, two *Mentorship Formalization* sub-themes emerged from the analysis: *Structured Mentorship* and *Mentor Engagement* (Appendix E).

Structured Mentorship

Structured Mentorship represents students' needs of both the general organization of the mentorship program and specific facets of mentorship they identified, some of which are to occur at specific intervals. Examples of respondents requesting more structure to mentorship include common short responses by students such as "Formalize it," "More Structured," and "Consistent mentor throughout the program." Other responses elaborated on the downsides of informal mentorship, as one student described, "My mentor was basically unavailable. I've

spoken to them like twice the entire program. Some kind of actually structured contact between mentor/mentee”.

Additionally, *Structured Mentorship* contains the study participants’ need for prescribed mentor and mentee expectations. Several responses highlighted that an organized start establishing the mentor-mentee relationship is vital to provide a formal foundation for the mentorship program. This is apparent in student responses such as “Perhaps before the semester starts, mentors can establish an effective means of communication and a plan for the mentor/mentee relationship.” Another participant echoed similar needs while expressing the importance of pre-defined expectations, “A more organized start to the mentorship, maybe a school scheduled meet and greet to set clearer expectations at the beginning of mentorship, ‘buddy’ and ‘mentor’ expectations can be different based upon individual need.” Students further expressed *Structured Mentorship* ideals by indicating the need for scheduled meetings throughout the program and defined roles of mentor and mentee.

Mentor Engagement

Aside from responses specifically addressing a regimented mentorship program, students desire increased opportunities to socialize with mentors to facilitate the mentor-mentee relationship through less formal means. It is from these expressed needs that the sub-theme of *Mentor Engagement* emerged. This sub-theme expresses the general desire for more school promotion of mentorship and social events or mixers that facilitate mentor-mentee interaction. Unique to this sub-theme is the inferred request to facilitate interaction between several mentors and mentees as a group rather than the focus on the one-on-one mentorship relationship of *Structured Mentorship*. For example, one student answered, “More networking events. Getting everyone together”, and another, “Opportunity to interact with upper and lower classmates.”

Although the sub-themes of *Mentorship Formalization* contain some unique elements, a few elements can be ascribed to both *Structured Mentorship* and *Mentor Engagement*. For example, responses highlighting the student need for a yearly mentorship mixer event, such as “Facilitate introduction with a mixer at the beginning of each year, define expectations of role,” possess elements indicating the want for increased structure and engagement simultaneously.

Discussion

The purpose of this project was to obtain baseline stress and mentorship satisfaction levels from current KPSA cohorts to be used in conjunction with current literature to make recommendations for the future implementation of a formal mentorship program at KPSA. After surveying students, qualitative and quantitative means were utilized to gain a greater insight into stress levels, mentorship satisfaction, and the needs of SRNAs at KPSA. Descriptive statistics were employed to describe demographic data. Multivariate analysis utilizing SPSS was used to test for variability between the three cohorts. Numbers and percentages were obtained from the data collected from the MET and PSS. Lastly, the qualitative data obtained from the open-ended questions was organized into codes using NVivo software. Codes were generated based on data obtained, and using thematic analysis themes were identified and defined.

Based on descriptive analyses, a moderate income level may play a role in decreasing stress, as evidenced by participants within median income levels ranging from \$25,001 to \$75,000 having substantially lower stress levels as compared with mean PSS scores for the lowest income bracket. There may also be gender-based differences in stress levels, wherein females may experience higher levels of stress as compared to their male counterparts. This difference is likely multifactorial and may include issues with societal roles and expectations, stressors that only females would understand and experience, and possibly that females are more likely to report stressors.

Another important facet of peer mentorship is its profound ability to alleviate stress. A statistically significant reduction in stress was demonstrated in graduate students by measuring stress utilizing the PSS in peer-mentored students compared to a control group who did not receive mentorship (Greene, 2021). This study's findings are consistent with Greene (2021)

demonstrating that higher mentorship satisfaction is associated with lower stress levels, as depicted in the linear regression analysis between mean mentorship satisfaction and PSS scores. These findings are also consistent with the study by Wang et al. (2022) where undergraduate nurses had a decline in their Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale scores after receiving mentorship. The results suggest that SRNAs who receive guidance from their mentors regarding clinicals and didactic were likely better prepared and knew what to expect, resulting in decreased overall stress. The literature also highlighted the need for educational institutions to prioritize the promotion of wellness, work-life balance, self-care, and support from faculty and peers to prevent negative consequences (Downey et al., 2017; Mesisca & Mainwaring, 2021). Unsurprisingly, the students that were surveyed strongly desired mentor support for stressors such as time management, school-life balance, stress, navigating financial burdens, and emotional support.

In addition, being employed at least part-time is associated with higher perceived stress scores, suggesting that increased stress levels may be attributed to increased responsibility and less time while working and in school. The lack of time as a stressor was also prevalent in the literature resulting in SRNAs being unable to spend time with their social support systems (Conner, 2015).

Higher parental education levels was a variable that was repeatedly represented in the results. Greater levels of mentorship satisfaction correlated with higher parental education; additionally, parental education was inversely related to perceived stress. The findings imply that perhaps SRNAs with parents who had higher levels of education learned methods for stress reduction from them. This parallels the literature that reveals the benefits of earlier emotional

and academic support from social sources, enabling SRNAs to create better coping mechanisms utilized in the duration of their program (Conner, 2015).

The themes that emerged from qualitative analysis, *Seeking Resilience* and *Mentorship Formalization*, represent the potential positive impact students believe near-peer mentors can have during their school experience and their ideal form of a mentorship program (Appendix E). Within the *Seeking Resilience* theme lies the challenges and stressors students face during their adjustment and growth as student nurse anesthetists. *Seeking Resilience* is accompanied by the marked belief that mentors can and should significantly aid students in navigating these challenges successfully. Although students can clearly identify many benefits of mentorship, the informal nature of the current program is a significant barrier to building and maintaining a successful relationship with mentors. Therefore, the needs expressed in the *Mentorship Formalization* theme are as vital to mentorship as the benefits mentors themselves provide. Findings among KPSA students were consistent with the literature in that they strongly desire a formal mentorship program (Downey et al., 2017; Johnson, 2018; Laurence et al., 2020). Kaiser students suggested the utilization of a matching program, scheduled mentor meetings, social events, and even more defined mentor-mentee roles highlighting the need for organizational support and coordination. Similarly, SRNAs from previous studies identified that a mentorship program integrated into the curriculum helped with guidance and support for students (Downey et al., 2017; Johnson, 2018). Several KPSA students also reported their mentors were not often available which was consistently described in the literature as a shortcoming of informal mentorship potentially due to either party's lack of availability, issues with communication, or lack of interest (Downey et al., 2017).

Recommendations

It is recommended that this school, as well as any others interested in implementing mentorship opportunities for students, adopt a formalized peer-mentorship program as the literature indicated this is the most successful form of mentorship (Farlow et al., 2021; Laurence et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2014). Moreover, our qualitative analysis of student responses revealed students strongly desire a structured approach to mentorship. As highlighted by SRNA responses, this should involve the use of a mentor-mentee matching system (Lawrence et al., 2020). Additionally, as KPSA students indicated in the free response questionnaire, time is often a barrier; therefore, university scheduled events would ensure that SRNA's time is protected and that they are able to focus on the material being presented (Conner, 2015; Downey et al., 2017; Johnson, 2018; Nolan et al., 2022).

It is also recommended that multiple PSS studies are conducted to better understand how stress levels change throughout the program. The PSS scores obtained reflect how students felt at one point in the three-year DNP program. The class of 2023 was a month away from graduating, 2024 was in the midst of an intense year of clinical training, and the class of 2025 had not yet started clinical rotations. It would be beneficial to track how PSS scores change and identify trends throughout the program in relation to significant milestones such as starting clinical rotations, beginning and then ending the DNP project, and even graduating. Mesisca and Mainwaring (2021) recommended integrating surveys at the end of each semester to evaluate student progression. This would also enable faculty to identify trends in student stress levels and provide timely interventions including but not limited to additional mentorship opportunities.

As SRNAs progress in the program, they have increased clinical hour requirements, likely leading to increases in stress levels during periods of higher clinical demands; therefore,

tracking stress levels as often as students change clinical sites may be beneficial but not entirely feasible as students may not have the time or energy to complete surveys every month. Although only MET and PSS scores from a single timepoint were collected, three distinct yet relatively homogeneous groups of SRNAs at various stages in their DNP curriculum are represented in the data. Tracking scores throughout the program may assist program administrators in understanding how and when students would benefit most from additional mentorship efforts.

Open-response survey questions were an accessible option to collect student experiences for thematic analysis and establish students' needs. However, it is recommended that future studies consider one-on-one interview techniques (Austin & Haplin, 2021), enabling researchers to ask follow-up questions to obtain richer responses for further analysis.

Another recommendation is that KPSA integrate wellness into the mentorship program. The literature and qualitative data strongly advocate well-being as a high priority for SRNAs that can be accomplished via workshops on self-care and stress reduction to tools for studying and relaxation (Downey et al., 2017; Johnson, 2018; Nolan et al., 2022). When combined, these recommendations will serve as a strong foundation for the future mentorship initiative at KPSA.

Implications

Based on the results from this study, it is apparent that all cohorts from KPSA demonstrated moderate stress levels, and it can be inferred that while students' actual stress levels vary, they are never very far from moderate. Additionally, the strongest correlations with increased stress were reduced income and working, which are unfortunately directly related and underscore the tremendous financial need students possess. While mentorship may help mitigate stress during the program, it is clear a variety of methods must be employed to alleviate as much stress as possible for SRNAs. Students do value the benefits of mentorship, as evidenced by the

theme *Seeking Resilience*, while *Mentorship Formalization* identifies informal mentorship as a significant barrier to students seeking consistent, involved mentorship.

Strengths and Limitations

There were several limitations that exist and should be considered with the results obtained. It is important to note that although there was a correlation between higher levels of mentorship satisfaction and lower perceived stress levels, we cannot assume causality between the two. The generalizability of the study results is affected by the small sample size, predominantly female participants, and higher participation rates from the class of 2024 compared to the other cohorts. Various factors, including stress levels and the amount of mentorship desired may vary between cohorts, which could ultimately affect participation rates and outcomes from the surveys. The youngest age group also only had one participant as compared to the other age groups, which also may have misrepresented the PSS scores of that group. Additionally, any of the survey questions were allowed to be omitted, including the demographic questions. The omission of questions may have skewed the results of the study.

Additionally, the survey was conducted at one point in a three-year program, with each cohort being in vastly different stages of their anesthesia education, and it must be stated that students' perceived levels of stress and mentorship satisfaction are dynamic and subject to variability throughout their three-year doctoral programs. This is a limitation of the pretest-posttest design and poses a threat to internal validity in that there could be other variables that impact the perceived stress levels of SRNAs or their opinion of the mentorship program. Lastly, the authors are themselves SRNAs at the program in which the survey was conducted and are therefore subject to bias.

The two greatest strengths of this DNP project are the use of validated survey instruments and open-ended questions to obtain data from SRNAs. The thematic analysis of open-ended questions enabled the research team to provide KPSA specific recommendations and to capture a richer set of data that would not be evoked with most other survey instruments. The homogeneity of the three DNP cohorts allows for a group, class of 2024, that is representative of the respondents to be reflective of what the two other cohorts would experience in their second year of the DNP program. Moreover, female students make up the majority of each cohort therefore, while the results may seem biased, they are an accurate reflection of the student population.

Conclusion

In summary, the primary data sources include electronic PSS and MET surveys distributed to current nurse anesthesia students alongside open-response questions. Evaluation methods consisted of utilizing descriptive statistics to describe baseline stress and mentorship satisfaction and effectiveness alongside thematic analysis of mentorship needs of the participants. This baseline data will be useful for future researchers seeking to implement and evaluate the peer-mentorship program at this school of nurse anesthesia.

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Appendix A

The Iowa Model

The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

Appendix B

Institutional Review Board Approval

Figure B1

California State University Fullerton Approval

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON

Office of Research and Sponsored Projects
P.O. Box 6850 or 1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd Fl., Fullerton, CA 92831 / T 657-278-7719 / F 657-278-7238

APPROVAL NOTICE

*From the Institutional Review Board
California State University, Fullerton*

April 21, 2023

**From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair
CSUF Institutional Review Board**

To: PI: Rachel McClanahan

Application No. HSR-22-23-331
Study Title: KPSA: Developing A Student Nurse Anesthetist Mentorship Program

Re: Initial Exempt Review

The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human participants in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University, Fullerton, Institutional Review Board. Your proposal is determined to be Category 2 (ii) Research that only includes interactions involving educational tests (cognitive, diagnostic, aptitude, achievement), survey procedures, interview procedures, or observation of public behavior (including visual or auditory recording). Any disclosure of the human subjects' responses outside the research would not reasonably place the subjects at risk of criminal or civil liability or be damaging to the subjects' financial standing, employability, educational advancement, or reputation.

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any departmental or additional approvals which may be required.

In addition, all research personnel must follow the institutional safety guidelines outlined for CSUF's Presidential Directive 22. Additional information can be found in the [TITANS RETURN: COVID-19 Recovery website](#).

Figure B2*Kaiser Permanente Approval***InterOffice Memorandum**

March 3, 2023

To: Dr. Jennifer Thompson
100 S. Los Robles Ave. #501
Pasadena CA 91101

Re: Developing a Student Nurse Anesthetist Mentorship Program

Dear Dr. Thompson,

A designated reviewer on the Kaiser Permanente Southern California (KPSC) Institutional Review Board (IRB) reviewed your submission and determined that this is not human subjects research as defined by 45 CFR 46.102 (e)(1) and (l). Therefore, IRB review of this project is not necessary.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Armida Ayala".

Armida Ayala, MHA, PhD
Director of Human Research Subjects Protection
Office/Institutional Review Board (IRB)

Figure C2

Perceived Stress Scale

PSS

INSTRUCTIONS:

The questions in this scale ask you about your feelings and thoughts during **THE LAST MONTH**. In each case, please indicate your response by placing an "X" over the circle representing **HOW OFTEN** you felt or thought a certain way.

	Never	Almost Never	Sometimes	Fairly Often	Very Often
	0	1	2	3	4
1. In the last month, how often have you been upset because of something that happened unexpectedly?	<input type="radio"/>				
2. In the last month, how often have you felt that you were unable to control the important things in your life?	<input type="radio"/>				
3. In the last month, how often have you felt nervous and "stressed"?	<input type="radio"/>				
4. In the last month, how often have you felt confident about your ability to handle your personal problems?	<input type="radio"/>				
5. In the last month, how often have you felt that things were going your way?	<input type="radio"/>				
6. In the last month, how often have you found that you could not cope with all the things that you had to do?	<input type="radio"/>				
7. In the last month, how often have you been able to control irritations in your life?	<input type="radio"/>				
8. In the last month, how often have you felt that you were on top of things?	<input type="radio"/>				
9. In the last month, how often have you been angered because of things that were outside your control?	<input type="radio"/>				
10. In the last month, how often have you felt difficulties were piling up so high that you could not overcome them?	<input type="radio"/>				

Figure C3*Open Response Questions*

What topics or areas do you feel you need additional mentorship in, currently or in the future?

(Free response)

In the past, what topics or areas do you feel would have benefited from additional mentorship?

(Free response)

In your opinion, how can the School of Anesthesia's mentoring plan be improved?

(Free response)

Appendix D

Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Demographic	n	%
KPSA Cohort		
2023	9	19.1%
2024	16	34.0%
2025	12	25.5%
Omitted	10	21.3%
Sex		
Male	19	40.4%
Female	28	59.6%
Age		
18-24	1	2.1%
25-34	42	89.4%
35-44	4	8.5%
Race		
White	17	36.2%
Hispanic or Latino	6	12.8%
Black or African American	1	2.1%
Asian	18	38.3%
Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander	1	2.1%
Other	4	8.5%
Marital Status		
Single	24	51.1%
Married or in a domestic partnership	23	48.9%
Employment Status		
Employed part time	3	6.4%
Unemployed and currently looking for work	1	2.1%
Student	43	91.5%
ICU Experience		
1 to 2 years	4	8.5%
3 to 5 years	29	61.7%
5 to 7 years	12	25.5%
7 to 9 years	2	4.3%
Highest Level of Education for Participant		
Bachelor's	43	91.5%

Master's	3	6.4%
Doctorate or professional degree	1	2.1%
Highest Level of Education for Parents		
Some high school or less	8	17.0%
High school diploma or GED	5	10.6%
Associate's or technical degree	3	6.4%
Bachelor's degree	21	44.7%
Graduate or professional	10	21.3%
Total Household Income		
Less than 25,000	22	46.8%
25,001 to 49,999	2	4.3%
50,000 to 74,999	1	2.1%
75,000 to 99,000	5	10.6%
100,000 to 149,000	9	19.1%
150,000 or more	4	8.5%
Prefer not to say	4	8.5%
Number of Dependents		
None	43	91.5%
1 to 2	3	6.4%
3 to 4	1	2.1%

Appendix E

Themes and Sub-themes

